

ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF INDUSTRY NETWORKS IN PROVIDING SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC GROWTH RATE

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Abstract. The article highlights the importance of economic reforms in the development of industrial sectors in ensuring sustainable economic growth. In addition, the state of development of industrial sectors to ensure sustainable economic growth has been analytically studied, and suggestions and recommendations have been made for their development.

Key words: sustainable economic growth, industrial sectors, sector diversification, economic reforms, structural changes.

As a consistent continuation of the reforms on the sustainable development of industrial sectors, a number of regulatory and legal documents related to the sector were adopted in the last five years. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to increase the industrial potential of the regions" was adopted. The decree is significant for the creation of a comprehensive system that supports the rapid development of local industries, as well as for increasing the industrial potential of the regions.

Many regulatory legal documents on the development of industrial sectors have been adopted and are being implemented. In particular, with the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to create favorable conditions for the further development of the jewelry industry", opportunities such as extending the payment period for the purchase of silver products have been created for manufacturers in the jewelry industry.

The adoption of the decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to organize and hold regional and republican inter-sectoral industrial fairs in 2021" creates wide opportunities for the development of the sector.

The adoption of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 12.10.2023 "On additional measures for the rapid development of industry and its basic sectors" No. It's done. As the main tasks mentioned in this decree, it is worth saying that today the rapid development of high-tech industries in the country, expanding the production of competitive finished products by attracting private investments in industrial sectors, increasing the income of the population due to the establishment of new production facilities in

the regions and large in order to introduce a management system based on advanced international standards to industries, the Ministry of Economy and Finance is entrusted with a number of tasks and functions for the implementation of the state industrial policy and the development of basic industries.

On the basis of economic reforms aimed at ensuring stable and proportionate growth of industrial sectors in our republic, production of competitive, exportable and import-substituting products with high added value, modernization of production capacities of industrial sectors, technological upgrading and large industrial enterprises the main emphasis is placed on issues such as creation. Such urgent and pending issues are the demand of today's times.

The role of industrial sectors in ensuring the economy and employment of the population of our republic is very important. Also, in order to create the necessary conditions for the industry, 19 free economic zones and more than 400 small industrial zones were established in recent years, and 10 trillion soums were allocated to their infrastructure. 3 billion dollars of financial resources have been allocated to turn industries such as textiles, chemicals, building materials, leather, pharmaceuticals, and electrical engineering into today's "drivers". In order to supply industry with raw materials, geological exploration has been tripled and more than 600 new mining reserves have been discovered.

The head of our country emphasized that new opportunities and additional financial resources will be provided for the industry. The first possibility is that banking regulations will be revised and additional resources of 55 trillion soums will be provided for allocating loans to enterprises in commercial banks. This is an additional resource for an average investment of 20 million dollars in one district.

The second possibility is that in 2023, 1.7 trillion soums will be allocated for the infrastructure of industrial zones and large investment projects. Also, the territory of "Gijduvan" and "Kokan" free economic zones will be expanded. Branches of the "Urgut" free economic zone will be established in Karakalpakstan and Kashkadarya.

The third possibility is that starting from 2023, 60 districts of the fourth and fifth categories with lagging economic development will be given 27 types of tax concessions, subsidies and preferences.

The fourth option is reliefs for the carpet, home textile, leather and jewelry industries. According to him, an additional 300 million dollars will be allocated to textile projects in 2023. Customs privileges on more than 200 types of imported raw materials in the leather-footwear industry will be extended for three years. Jewelers are given the opportunity to purchase raw materials at a discount, as well as tax, customs and banking benefits.

As urgent issues highlighted by the President, the implementation of localization projects worth 6 billion dollars in the regions and the timely launch of about 3 thousand projects included in the regional investment programs at the expense of expanding industrial cooperation were determined.

Today, 69,400 industrial enterprises are operating in the republic, of which 11,800 (17.0% of the total number of registered enterprises) are in Tashkent, 7,800 (11.2%) are in Farg. to the mother region, 7.3 thousand (10.5%) to Tashkent region, 6.2 thousand (8.9%) to Samarkand region and 5.5 thousand (7.9%) to Andijan region.

Industry is a branch of production that includes the processing of raw materials, the exploitation of underground resources, the creation of means of production and consumer goods. According to preliminary data, in January-December 2023, 655.8 trillion will be spent by republican enterprises. Sums worth of industrial products were produced, and compared to January-December 2022, the physical volume index of industrial production was 106.0%. The index of the physical volume of industrial production is a relative indicator describing the change in the volume of manufactured products (works, services) in comparable periods.

Due to the distribution of production of industrial products per capita, the location of large industrial enterprises in Navoi region (95,361.7 thousand soums), Tashkent city (41,228.9 thousand soums) and Tashkent region (34,990.5 thousand soums) m) is significantly higher than the average national level (18,011,000 soums).

Tashkent city (18.9%), Tashkent region (16.1%), Navoi region 15.5%), Andijan region (11.2%) and Farg have a high share in total industrial production in the republic in January-December 2023. Mother region contributed (5.6%). Also, compared to the corresponding period of the previous year, high FHI was observed in Jizzakh region (107.4%), Andijan region (107.3%) and Namangan region (107.2%).

In conclusion, these opportunities created for the development of industrial sectors, reforms to ensure stable economic growth rates of industrial sectors will give their practical results in the future.

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